

Synthesis of Some Pyrazolines and Iso-oxazolines

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The chalcones contain an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated grouping in its molecule and react with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride very readily, affording pyrazolines and iso-oxazolines, respectively^{1,2}. In the present work, the preparation of fluorinated pyrazolines and iso-oxazolines derived from fluoro-chalcones, previously synthesised³⁻⁴, is reported.

In boiling acetic acid medium, the chalcones react with phenylhydrazine to yield phenylhydrazones which immediately rearrange to the corresponding isomeric 1-phenyl-3,5-(substituted phenyl)- Δ^2 -pyrazolines (I). The iso-oxazoline (II) derivatives were obtained on refluxing a pyridine solution of the fluoro-chalcone and hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Pyrazolines.—The required chalcone (1 g.) was added to phenylhydrazine (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid⁵ (10 ml) and the reaction mixture refluxed for 3 hr. After cooling, the resultant mass was diluted and the solid separating was recrystallised from ethanol. These derivatives, when placed on a filter paper and exposed to bromide vapour, turn green and have been identified as pyrazolines¹. The pyrazolines prepared are recorded in Table I.

Iso-oxazolines.—To a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.2 g.) in water (5 ml) were added the requisite chalcone (1 g.) and pyridine² (10 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr., acidified with dilute acetic acid, and left overnight. The solid, thus obtained, was recrystallised from benzene. Iso-oxazolines synthesised are reported in Table II.

1. Raiford and Peterson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1937, 1, 544.
2. Samour, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 1067.
3. Joshi and Jauhar, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 463.
4. *Idem*, under publication.
5. Raval *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 323.

TABLE I

1-Phenyl-3,5-(substituted phenyl)- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (I).

Chalkones.	R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
4'-Fluoro-C	4''-Fluoro-	..	126°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ F	8.25	8.58
3'-Methyl-4''-fluoro-C	3''-Methyl-4''-fluoro-	..	90°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ F	8.10	8.48
4,4'-Difluoro-C	4''-Fluoro-	4-Fluoro-	120-21°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ F ₂	8.00	8.38
3'-Methyl-4,4'-difluoro-C	3''-Methyl-4''-fluoro-	4'-Fluoro-	108°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ F ₂	7.81	8.04
5'-Methyl-2',4-difluoro-C	5''-Methyl-2''-fluoro-	4'-Fluoro-	95°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ F ₂	7.90	8.04
2'-Hydroxy-3,4-methy- lenedioxy-5'-fluoro-C	2''-Hydroxy- 5''-fluoro-	3',4'-Methy- lenedioxy-	93-94°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ F	7.11	7.44

N. B. C stands for chalkone.

TABLE II

3,5-(Substituted phenyl)- Δ^2 -iso-oxazoline (II).

Chalkone.	R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4'-Fluoro-C	4''-Fluoro-	..	180°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ONF	5.54	5.80
4,4'-Difluoro-C	4''- ,,	4'-Fluoro-	191°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ONF ₂	5.11	5.40
3'-Methyl-4'-fluoro-C	3''-Methyl-4''-fluoro-	..	173°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ONF	5.32	5.49
3'-Methyl-4,4'-difluoro-C	3''-Methyl-4''-fluoro-	4'-Fluoro-	175°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ONF	4.94	5.12
5'-Methyl-3, 4-methy- lenedioxy-2'-fluoro-C	5''-Methyl-2''-fluoro-	3',4'-Methy- lenedioxy-	135°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ NF	4.12	4.68
3'-Methyl-3,4-methy- lenedioxy-4'-fluoro-C	3''-Methyl-4''-fluoro-	Do	140-41°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ NF	4.40	4.68

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